

ADAPT Study Registration Policy

Overview

ADAPT-funded studies must be registered to osf.io/registries. This policy establishes what to register, when, and how – with requirements tailored to two study types: Exploratory and Confirmatory.

The policy seeks to achieve two benefits for the scientific community.

- **Increase transparency**, by enabling others to trace the research process from inception to completion, assess risks of bias, and calibrate their confidence in the resulting methods and outcomes.
- **Reduce risk of bias** by encouraging outcome-independent decision-making in confirmatory studies.

If you have questions about how these requirements apply to your study, contact ADAPT staff.

Study Types

This policy separates Exploratory Studies from Confirmatory Studies and establishes a set of requirements for each. Note that a single ADAPT-funded project may contain both types of studies.

- **Exploratory Studies.** Research focused on generating new hypotheses, collecting pilot data, or developing experimental methods and tools (e.g., establishing standard operating procedures, producing novel experimental stimuli).
- **Confirmatory Studies.** Research designed to test pre-specified hypotheses, systematically validate established experimental methods and tools, or replicate established findings.

Policy Requirements for Exploratory Studies

Exploratory Studies are registered to provide a transparent record of a team's research goals and intended methods at the time of registration.

1. Repository and License

Registrations must be deposited to <https://osf.io/registries> ([instructions are available on the OSF Website here](#)) with a CC BY 4.0 license or a CCo public domain dedication. Clinical trials must additionally be deposited to [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov) or [a primary registry in the WHO registry network](#) and those clinical trial registrations must link to the registration on <https://osf.io/registries>.

2. Content

The registration should contain sufficient detail to allow a third-party to understand the study objectives, methods, and analytic approaches. The registration must identify whether there are hypotheses, sample size calculations, and pre-planned analyses (i.e., if there are none, simply indicate none). Various registration templates are available; the [PRP-QUANT Template](#) is a good option to help ensure a thorough study registration.

Note that the initial submission can be brief, with the expectation that details of methods and analysis plans get added as they evolve and would be informative to third-party users of the data and results.

3. Registration Timing

A registration should be deposited before data collection begins or as promptly as possible after data collection begins. It is understood that there may be considerable piloting required to refine data collection procedures before the registration. For studies using pre-existing data, registrations should state how familiar the researchers are with the data.

4. Embargo Period

The registration must be publicly available or in a repository with a fixed embargo period. The registration cannot only be in the research team's possession. If an embargo is applied:

- It must be lifted no later than the time of posting an associated preprint.
- It must not exceed 24 months from the date of registration without prior approval from ADAPT staff.

We encourage public availability of registrations as early as possible, without compromising the scientific validity or integrity of a study.

5. Linkage

All scripts, protocols, and other materials available at the time of registration (e.g., participant instructions) must be contained within your registration, or cited in your registration using a persistent identifier (e.g., a Digital Object Identifier – DOI).

6. Reporting

Papers, including preprints, that report results from the registered study must identify that the study was registered and cite the registration DOI and/or trial registration number.

7. Registration Updates

We encourage updating the registered plan to provide a record of how the methods and analysis approaches evolved ([instructions here](#)). It is productive for the community to understand paths that fail as much as those that ultimately succeed. When updating a registration, a brief description of what changed and why it was changed is helpful context for future readers of the record.

Policy Requirements for Confirmatory Studies

Confirmatory studies must meet all requirements listed above for Exploratory Studies, plus the additional requirements described in this section. Where a requirement below extends or replaces a requirement for exploratory studies, that is noted explicitly.

1. Content (Extension for Confirmatory Studies)

Confirmatory study registrations must contain enough information to be "producible" ([see glossary](#)), in the sense that another researcher in your discipline – after reading your registration and associated scripts and protocols – could produce the study described in the registration. We recommend using a registration template. ADAPT staff have created a modified version of the PRP-QUANT Template for [human research](#) and [preclinical research](#), which you may use. These templates are tailored to address the requirements of this policy.

2. Registration Timing (Extension for Confirmatory Studies)

Confirmatory studies must be registered before data collection begins, without exception. Late registration of a confirmatory study defeats the core purpose of this policy and is not permitted. For confirmatory studies using pre-existing data, when possible, registration should occur before exploring the dataset.

3. Hypothesis Itemization

The registration must contain itemized, operationalized hypotheses. All other sections of the registration must identify which hypotheses they relate to. For example, a study registration may include 5 distinct hypotheses. The statistical analyses (including sample size calculations) associated with each hypothesis should be unambiguously associated with that hypothesis.

4. Sample Size Calculations

Registrations must contain sample size calculations (precision, power, or sensitivity – [see glossary](#) for definitions). Be sure to include:

- **Justification.** Selected effect sizes, or margins of error, must [be justified](#) and matched to a hypothesis in your registration. We recommend selecting effect sizes based on clinical, biological, or practical significance ([see glossary](#)) rather than focusing exclusively on statistical significance.
- **Units.** Sample size calculations must [unambiguously define 'N'](#) and identify any associated nesting structure (e.g., observing dendrites, within treated neurons, from mice).
- **Hypothesis match.** Sample size calculations must match a hypothesis, rather than an overarching research question. For example, in a study with 3 groups, the sample size should be selected based on pairwise comparisons rather than an ANOVA. This allows researchers to conclude that one group outperformed another group, rather than only establishing that the 3 groups differed.

5. Executable Code

The registration must use a persistent identifier to point to executable scripts. This may include statistical analyses, data processing (e.g., for fMRI), sample size calculations, randomized assignment, and experimental scripts (e.g., the visual presentation of a psychometric task). A competent researcher in your discipline should be able to run the scripts using only the information contained or cited within the registration. For data types that can reasonably be deposited alongside scripts (e.g., tabular data) we recommend including test datasets (e.g., simulated data, previously collected data, or another type of representative data) to facilitate running the scripts.

We recommend depositing these scripts to GitHub, and using Zenodo to generate a persistent identifier for the registered version of the code ([instructions here](#)), then citing both the GitHub URL and the Zenodo DOI in your registration. These scripts must come with a license that allows for unrestricted reuse (e.g., MIT license).

6. Recipe-Style Protocols

For aspects of your study that will not be scripted using code (e.g., wet-lab procedures, manual assessments), you should cite the existing recipe-style protocol or scoring manual, or deposit and cite a new step-by-step protocol or manual. Protocols must come with a CC BY 4.0 license or CCo public domain dedication.

7. Completeness Check

ADAPT staff perform completeness checks to ensure each Confirmatory Study registration addresses the requirements of this policy. The workflow is as follows:

- Grantees submit a draft registration to ADAPT staff. Within 10 business days, ADAPT staff return a completeness review with feedback to be addressed, or approval for data collection to begin
- Once the approved registration is deposited, data collection may begin

8. Reporting (Extension for Confirmatory Studies)

Papers must identify which specific hypotheses, analyses, data collection procedures, and other steps were registered and which were not. Unregistered analyses must be clearly labeled as exploratory.

9. Registration Updates (Extension for Confirmatory Studies)

If you make substantive updates to your registered study plans, we recommend you update your registration by adding a file outlining the deviations (e.g., by using the [PRP-QUANT Deviation Template](#) or [this more general template](#)). Updating your registration provides a time-stamp showing when the updates were made, while also maintaining access to the original registration.

Example Registration Package for a Confirmatory Study

A complete registration package for an ADAPT-funded confirmatory study could include the following:

OSF Registries

- The registration itself (e.g., a completed version of the PRP-QUANT template), which uses persistent identifiers to cite the materials below

GitHub & Zenodo

- Statistical analysis scripts
- Test datasets, to facilitate running the scripts
- Preprocessing scripts
- Sample size calculation scripts
- Randomization scripts
- Scripted tasks (e.g., for psychometric testing)

Protocols.io

- Step-by-step instructions for wet-lab procedures and manual assessments
- Non-scripted preprocessing and analysis workflows

Relationship to Other ADAPT Policies

This policy operationalizes the second requirement of the [ADAPT Open Science Policy](#) and governs study registration only. It should be read alongside the ADAPT Open Science Policy, which covers data deposit, access, and licensing requirements.

- **Registration vs. data deposit:** [osf.io/registries](#) is the designated platform for study registrations. Bridge Analytics is the designated platform for data deposition. These are complementary systems; registration on OSF does not fulfill data deposit obligations under the Open Science Policy.

Glossary

Registration

A persistent document that declares a research plan (for example, hypotheses, design and statistical analyses) in a public registry before the research outcomes are known ([Hardwicke and Wagenmakers, 2023](#)). For the purposes of the ADAPT Study Registration Policy, we stick to the term Registration. Our use of this term is largely interchangeable with the terms Prospective Registration and Preregistration.

Prospective Registration

A Registration that is deposited in a public registry before data are collected (for studies with data collection) or before exploration of existent data (for studies using pre-existing data).

Retrospective Registration

A Registration that is deposited in a public registry after data collection begun, after data were explored, or after study completion.

Preregistration

This term is mostly interchangeable with Prospective Registration, but has a different origin. Clinical trials research uses the term prospective registration, whereas many other disciplines use the term preregistration. Prospective registration of clinical trials differs from preregistration of research in other disciplines in terms of its history, the functions it was designed to serve, and implementation details (e.g., clinical trial registries do not include sections specifically dedicated to hypotheses or analysis plans).

Clinical Trial Registration

This is simply Registration, as defined above, for a clinical trial. Clinical Trial registration is highly regulated compared to preregistrations in other disciplines.

Producible Registration

A registration where all procedures are unambiguously detailed to the extent that independent researchers could run the study without requiring additional information.

Executable Registration

A registration that includes complete, pre-specified preprocessing and statistical analysis scripts that can be run without modification.

Precision Calculation

A sample size calculation based on achieving a specified margin of error or desired width of a confidence interval.

Power Calculation

A sample size calculation based on achieving a specified statistical power (typically 80% or 95%) to detect a minimum effect size of interest.

Sensitivity Calculation

A calculation of the minimum detectable effect size, given a fixed and known sample size.

Practical Significance

The magnitude of an effect size that is large enough to be meaningful in a real-world, clinical, biological, or theoretical context, independent of the p-value. For example, medical research often uses Minimal Clinically Important Differences (MCIDs) – defined as the smallest change in a treatment outcome that a patient can perceive.

Statistical Significance

The result of a hypothesis test, indicating that the observed effect is unlikely to be due to chance (often defined by a p-value threshold).

Exploratory Studies

Research focused on generating new hypotheses, collecting pilot data, or developing experimental methods and tools (e.g., establishing standard operating procedures, producing novel experimental stimuli).

Confirmatory Studies

Research designed to test pre-specified hypotheses, systematically validate established experimental methods and tools, or replicate established findings.

